

TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY AND THEIR PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 6

Pages: 686-700

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1995

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12633818

Manuscript Accepted: 05-31-2024

Teachers' Self-Efficacy and their Performance

Norjehan M. Sangcad,* Carlito A. Abarquez

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aims to determine the self-efficacy and work performance based on the DepEd Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) rating in 2022-2023 among the 120 teachers in the district, Sultan Naga Dimaporo Central, Division of Lanao del Norte. To provide the respondents' context their profile is described using the descriptive-correlational research design, with modified adapted questionnaire as the main data gathering tool. Data were analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistics. The respondents are predominantly male and female, married and single who are 23 to 50 years old, mainly bachelor's degree holders in education who have worked as DepEd teachers for at least one to five years. Respondents obtained a high self-efficacy level with very satisfactory work performance. Correlational analyses reveal that civil status, educational attainment, and length of DepEd teaching experience are significantly related to self-efficacy at 0.05 significance level. Correspondingly, self-efficacy in creating positive school environment, managing student discipline, and enlisting parental involvement are significantly related to teachers' work performance. The role of self-efficacy in achieving desired teachers' work performance is thus substantiated. To further enhance these dimensions of teaching profession towards developing competent learners, teachers must actively engage in relevant training activities, and pursue higher formal studies in education.

Keywords: *self-efficacy, teachers' performance, IPCRF rating*

Introduction

The positive learning environment is what learners need. A place where they could play safely, learn some knowledge, and attain skills that encourage them to come to school every day. Teachers must possess skills that could lead the school for the better. Further, teachers should build trust and foster positive working relationships not only inside the classroom but also outside the school environment, and act with fairness, dignity, and integrity because their roles, decisions, and strategies are important to learners' academic performance. Helping the learners to build up their self-esteem must be charted in the teachers' roadmaps.

As the researcher observed in the district, most of the teachers were not interested in participating in seminars and other appropriate training activities. Some schools got very low in terms of learner academic performance, and some learners were non-readers because one of the problems in the remote areas is absenteeism. The researcher believed that if the teacher has a high self-efficacy in teaching, she could probably produce learners who have high academic performance. The outcomes of teachers who have low self-efficacy are low-quality of teaching and low academic performance of the learners.

In this case, the school head must motivate the teachers and learners by providing financial and moral support. There are instances when learners lack confidence due to a lack of teacher motivation. A good teacher manages the classroom effectively and has a high self-efficacy, as well as allows parents to have access to the performance of their child. Teachers should establish a positive learning environment for the learners to boost their potential.

Since August 29, 2012, the researcher has been assigned as teacher I in Sultan Naga Dimaporo Memorial Integrated School and Sultan Naga Dimaporo Central District. The researcher observed that the teachers have not been actively on division-level academic competitions that can be beneficial to learners.

According to Slade (2017), a quality education is supported by three key pillars: ensuring access to quality teachers; providing the use of quality learning tools and professional development; and the establishment of safe and supportive quality learning environments. In the establishment of a safe and supportive quality learning environment, there should be a good relationship between the parents of the learners. The researcher, however, observed that most of the parents in the remote areas did not provide the necessary social support to their children. Cited in the article of Chowdhury (2019), self-efficacy is when we have a high degree of belief in our abilities to do certain things.

A creative person who aspires to become successful must trust his art before he steps out to reach his goals. As what the researcher observed, teachers in the particular district where she worked have a low self-confidence in expressing their selves. A local study on teacher's self-efficacy and related factors, however, is wanting. As the articles reviewed indicate, many of such studies were undertaken in foreign settings with some of which done in other areas in the Philippines. Certain differences may exist in the socio-cultural contexts. This study was an attempt to fill in this void in research.

The main purpose of this study was to assess the self-efficacy of the teachers in instruction, discipline among the learners, enlisting parental support and creating a positive classroom climate. Self-efficacy is subsequently correlated with teaching performance based on the IPCRF rating during the school year 2022-2023. The researcher is motivated to conduct this study having been a teacher herself

for years who have observed that teachers' efficacy is pivotal to the enhancement of learners' performance. The study is conducted within the district of Sultan Naga Dimaporo Central, Division of Lanao del Norte in the School Year 2022-2023.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to determine the level of self-efficacy of the teachers and their work performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) ratings during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age,
 - 1.2. sex,
 - 1.3. civil status,
 - 1.4. educational attainment, and
 - 1.5. years in a teaching position?
2. What is the self-efficacy of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. instructional self-efficacy,
 - 2.2. disciplinary self-efficacy,
 - 2.3. efficacy to enlist parents support, and
 - 2.4. efficacy to create a positive school climate?
3. What is the teaching performance of the teachers based on their IPCRF for SY 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondent's profile and self-efficacy?
5. Is there a significant relationship between self-efficacy and teacher's performance?
6. Which of the socio-economic profiles and the extent of self-efficacy variables significantly predict the teaching performance of the respondents?
7. What training program can be designed based from the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study was a descriptive-correlational design because it referred to one in which the researcher intended to determine the "extent to which two variables (or more) co-vary. It meant the changes in one variable were manifested in the other variable" (Creswell, 2012). In other words, the purpose of this design was to explain the relationship between two or among more than two variables. In this design, the data were collected at a single point in time. All participants were taken as one group, and at least two sets of scores were obtained for each individual in the group, that is, one for each variable. The use of the correlational statistical test was discussed, and interpretations and conclusions were based on the results of the correlation tests.

Respondents

A total of 120 teachers were involved in the study as primary sources of information, 113 of them were females and only 7 were male teachers. They comprised the entire teaching force of Sultan Naga Dimaporo Central District. In other words, the teacher-respondents constituted the complete enumeration of the population of the study. Below is the table showing the respondents of the study.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>School</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Pikalawag Integrated School	1	23	24
Sultan Naga Dimaporo Memorial Integrated School	2	33	35
Maguindanao Integrated School	2	14	16
Topocon Elementary School	1	4	5
Ramain Elementary School	1	15	16
Koreo Elementary School	0	8	8
Sugod Elementary School	0	7	7
Sigayan Elementary School	0	9	9
Total	7	113	120

Instruments

The main data gathering tools that were used were adopted from Bandura's teacher self-efficacy questionnaires. These were modified to include the IPCRF rating. It was used to obtain the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) rating of the teacher-respondents during the school year 2021-2022. This assessed their self-efficacy in terms of instructional self-efficacy, disciplinary self-efficacy, self-efficacy to enlist parental support, and self-efficacy to create a positive school climate. The instrument consisted of 29-item questions that measured self-efficacy on a five-point scale of influences where: 5 means a great deal, 4 means quite a bit, 3 means some influence, 2 means very little, and 1 means nothing.

Another feature of the questionnaire was the section on the demographic profile questionnaire which was added (Appendix A) to determine the characteristics of the teacher-respondents in terms of age, sex category, civil status, educational attainment, and years in teaching.

Procedure

For data gathering procedure, the researcher first constructed the set of questions on demographic profile in addition to the adopted 29-item self-efficacy questionnaire. Then a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) to seek approval to conduct the data gathering in the said schools was submitted. Upon the Schools Division Superintendent's approval of the request, a letter to the principal of each of the said schools was sent to secure approval for the field research. Thereafter, letters were sent to prospected teacher-respondents to seek their approval.

With the teacher's approval, the questionnaires were administered to the teacher-respondents. The respondents were given questionnaires, a demographic profile questionnaire, and a self-efficacy scale questionnaire. The demographic profile questionnaire was designed to determine the personal background and the self-efficacy scale questionnaire was designed to generate information on the perceived capacity of the teachers in instruction, student discipline, enlisting parental support, and creating a positive school climate. As soon as the accomplished questionnaires were retrieved, the data were processed and analyzed using appropriate data analysis methods.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented.

For problem 1, frequency and percentage were used to describe the profiles of the respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, occupation, and monthly family income.

For problem 2, mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to describe the level of self-efficacy of respondents in terms of instructional self-efficacy, disciplinary self-efficacy, efficacy in enlisting parents' support, and efficacy in creating a positive school climate.

For problem 3, frequency and percentage were used to describe the teaching performance of the respondents.

For problem 4, multiple regression analysis (simultaneous entry) was used to determine the association between the significant relationship of the respondents' profiles and self-efficacy. ANOVA for regression was used to measure the overall fit of the estimated model. Coefficient of multiple determination, r^2 was used to measure the proportion of total variation of the level of teachers' self-efficacy as explained by the respondents' profiles.

For problem 5, multiple regression analysis (simultaneous entry) was used to determine the association between the respondents' profiles and the teaching performance. ANOVA for regression was used to measure the overall fit of the estimated model. Coefficient of multiple determination, r^2 was used to measure the proportion of total variation of the extent of teaching performance as explained by the respondents' profiles.

For problem 6, Pearson correlation was used to determine the relationship between the level of self-efficacy and the teaching performance of the teachers. Multiple regression analysis (simultaneous entry) was used to investigate the association of the different indicators of self-efficacy and the teaching performance of the respondents. Coefficient of multiple determination, r^2 was used to measure the proportion of total variation of the level of teaching performance as explained by the level of self-efficacy.

For problem 7, multiple regression analysis (simultaneous entry) was used to determine the effect of respondents' profiles and level of self-efficacy variables to the teaching performance of the teachers. ANOVA for regression was used to measure the overall fit of the estimated model. Coefficient of multiple determination, r^2 was used to measure the proportion of total variation of the extent of teaching performance as explained by the respondents' profiles and extent of self-efficacy.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data in relevance to the reading dimension. For better analysis and interpretation, these data are presented in tabular and graphical forms. For authentic discussions, this chapter employs related literature and studies.

Problem 1: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex category, civil status, educational attainment, and years in teaching position?

Table 2. *Age Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Below-30	28	23.3
31-45	59	49.2
46-55	14	11.7
56-64	19	15.8
Total	120	100.0

Table 2 presents the age profile of the respondents in the study, categorizing them into four age groups. The majority of respondents, comprising 49.2%, fell within the age range of 31 to 45 years, indicating a significant presence of individuals in the prime of their professional and personal lives. The next largest group consisted of individuals below the age of 30, constituting 23.3% of the total respondents. This suggested a diverse participant pool, including both early-career professionals and those with more established experience. The older age groups, specifically those aged 46 to 55 and 56 to 64 years, represented 11.7% and 15.8% of the respondents, respectively, indicating a smaller but still noteworthy representation of individuals in the later stages of their careers.

It was a common observation that age influenced teaching because it was associated with no experiences (Bodhe et al., 2019). Accordingly, as the age advanced, teachers became experienced and they knew where to tap the potential of the students and how to make them understand their worth.

Table 3. Sex Profile of the Respondents

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Female	113	94.2
Male	7	5.8
Total	120	100.0

Table 3 presents the gender profile of the respondents in the study. The data clearly indicated a significant gender imbalance, with a substantial majority of 94.2% of the respondents identifying as female. In contrast, the male respondents constituted only a small proportion, amounting to 5.8% of the total sample. This gender distribution raised important considerations for the study, as the overwhelming female representation may influence the generalizability of findings to a broader population.

This implied that there were more female teachers than the males which meant that more female teachers were involved in the teaching profession. In a recent study by Shah et al. (2018) found that students were a little toward biased to female teachers, which may be related to a variety of factors like empathic listening, better, understanding, and view of concern shown by them.

Table 4. Civil Status Profile of the Respondents

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Single	23	19.2
Married	87	72.5
Widowed	10	8.3
Total	120	100.0

Table 4 provides insights into the civil status profile of the respondents in the study. The majority of the participants, constituting 72.5%, were married. This indicated a predominant presence of individuals who were currently in a marital relationship, suggesting that the study might have a substantial focus on individuals in family settings or partnerships. On the other hand, 19.2% of the respondents were single, representing a noteworthy portion of the sample who were not currently married. Additionally, 8.3% of the participants were widowed, signifying a smaller but still significant group who may bring unique perspectives and experiences to the study.

This implied that the majority of the teachers were married. The study carried out by Khurshid, Qasmi, and As-huraf (2019), found that marital status affected the self-efficacy of teachers and that married male and female teachers had high self-efficacy which led to high job performance.

Table 5 presents the educational attainment profile of the respondents, revealing a diverse range of academic achievements within the sample. The majority of participants, comprising 57.5%, were college graduates, indicating a substantial representation of individuals with undergraduate-level education. On the other hand, 42.5% of the respondents had attained a Master's degree, reflecting a significant presence of individuals with advanced levels of education. This distribution suggested a well-educated participant pool, with a balance between those who have completed their undergraduate studies and those who had pursued postgraduate education.

Table 5. Educational Attainment Profile of the Respondents

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
College Graduate	69	57.5
Master's Graduate	51	42.5
Total	120	100.0

According to Ponders (2020), teachers' educational attainment was correlational to their teaching skills and performance. He observed that the more teachers sought educational growth the more they became equipped with the necessary teaching methodologies to employ in the actual teaching.

Table 6 illustrates the distribution of the respondents based on their years in a teaching position. The data highlighted a diverse range of experience levels among the participants. The majority of respondents, accounting for 56.7%, had been in a teaching position for 11 to 20 years, indicating a significant presence of educators with a moderate level of experience.

Table 6. *Years in Teaching Position Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Years in Teaching Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1-10	8	6.7
11-20	68	56.7
21-30	41	34.2
31-40	3	2.5
Total	120	100.0

Additionally, 34.2% of the respondents fell within the 21 to 30 years' category, showcasing a substantial number of individuals with more extensive teaching experience. A smaller proportion, 6.7%, had been in a teaching position for 1 to 10 years, suggesting the inclusion of early-career educators in the sample.

The least represented category consisted of individuals with 31 to 40 years of teaching experience, comprising 2.5% of the total respondents. This distribution provided valuable context for understanding the professional backgrounds of the participants and allowed for considerations of how their varying levels of experience might influence their perspectives and contributions to the study.

The appointment status or working status of teachers, according to Omoifo et al. (2020), revealed that they work more to obtain a permanent status, which implies they consistently enhance their work ethics and manner of instruction.

Teaching experience was favorably correlated with student achievement over the course of a teacher's career, according to Biyani et al. (2019). The steepest increases in teacher effectiveness were seen in the first few years of their professions, but these gains persisted into the second and even third decades of their careers.

Problem 2: How do the respondents assess their self-efficacy in terms of instructional self-efficacy, disciplinary self-efficacy, efficacy in enlisting parents' support, and efficacy in creating a positive school climate?

Table 7. *Respondents' Assessment of their Self-Efficacy in terms of Instructional Self-Efficacy*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. How much can you do to influence the class sizes in your class?	4.75	0.43	Very High
2. How much can you do to get the most difficult students?	4.80	0.40	Very High
3. How much can you do to promote learning when there is a lack of support from the home?	4.73	0.45	Very High
4. How much can you do to keep students on task on difficult assignments?	4.98	0.26	Very High
5. How much can you do to increase students' memory of what they have been taught in previous lessons?	4.93	0.26	Very High
6. How much can you do to motivate students who have low interest in schoolwork?	4.83	0.38	Very High
7. How much can you do to get students to work together?	4.75	0.43	Very High
8. How much can you do to overcome the influence of advanced community conditions on students' learning?	4.73	0.45	Very High
9. How much can you do to get children to do their homework?	4.97	0.18	Very High
Total Measure	4.83	0.12	Very High

Note: Scale; Responses; Description; 1.00-1.49; Nothing; Very Low; 1.50-2.49; Very Little; Low; 2.50-3.49; Some Influence; Average; 3.50-4.49; Quite a Bit; High; 4.50-5.00; A Great Deal; Very High

Table 7 presents the respondents' self-assessment of their instructional self-efficacy across various indicators, with mean and standard deviation (SD) values provided for each. The respondents, on average, reported a high level of self-efficacy across all indicators, as indicated by the mean score of 4.83 with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.12, reflecting a consistent and collectively positive perception. The highest mean score was observed for the indicator related to keeping students on task on difficult assignments ($M=4.98$), followed closely by the ability to get children to do their homework ($M=4.97$). These findings suggested that, on average, the respondents feel highly confident in their capabilities to handle a range of instructional challenges.

The low standard deviations across all indicators indicated a high level of agreement among respondents regarding their perceived self-efficacy, reinforcing the overall homogeneity in their assessments. The consistently high mean scores across various instructional challenges signified a robust sense of confidence among the educators in their ability to influence classroom dynamics, address behavioral issues, and navigate external challenges.

These results showed that a collectively high level of instructional self-efficacy suggested a positive and empowering work environment, potentially contributing to increased job satisfaction and effectiveness. According to research, educators who had high levels of self-efficacy were more willing to try out new teaching techniques, set more ambitious objectives, were more organized and planned, focused on finding solutions to problems, asked for help when needed, and modified their lesson plans when things got tough (Reyes, 2020).

These efforts paid off for both the self-efficacious teachers—who experienced burnout less frequently and were happier in their roles—and their students—who demonstrated more drive, academic success, and adaptability. Collective teacher efficacy assisted in understanding the disparate effects of faculty and entire schools on student outcomes, while the self-efficacy of the individual teacher revealed how the individual teacher's views connected to students' academic progress. As a result, it was extremely pertinent to the

teaching setting to methodically investigate strategies that boost teacher self-efficacy (Stanton, 2019).

Table 8. Respondents' Assessment of their Self-Efficacy in terms of Disciplinary Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. How much can you do to get children to follow classroom rules?	4.80	0.40	Very High
2. How much can you do to control disruptive behavior in the classroom?	4.73	0.45	Very High
3. How much can you do to prevent problem behavior on the school grounds?	4.98	0.16	Very High
4. How much can you do to get involved the learners in every school activity?	4.93	0.26	Very High
5. How much can you do to get involved the learners in every District activity?	4.83	0.38	Very High
6. How much can you do to make the learners help each other during group activities?	4.75	0.43	Very High
Total Measure	4.83	0.18	Very High

Note: Scale; Responses; Description; 1.00-1.49; Nothing; Very Low; 1.50-2.49; Very Little; Low; 2.50-3.49; Some Influence; Average; 3.50-4.49; Quite a Bit; High; 4.50-5.00; A Great Deal; Very High

Table 8 presents the respondents' assessment of their disciplinary self-efficacy across various indicators, with mean and standard deviation (SD) values provided for each. The average mean score for overall disciplinary self-efficacy was 4.83, with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.18, indicating a consistent and high level of perceived self-efficacy in disciplinary matters.

The highest mean score was associated with the respondents' confidence in preventing problem behavior on the school grounds ($M=4.98$), emphasizing a strong belief in their ability to maintain a positive and orderly school environment. Other indicators, such as getting children to follow classroom rules ($M=4.80$) and involving learners in various school and district activities (4.83 and 4.93, respectively), also received high mean scores, further reflecting the educators' confidence in managing and engaging students effectively.

The low standard deviations across all indicators suggested a high level of agreement among respondents regarding their disciplinary self-efficacy, indicating a shared perception of competence in handling disciplinary issues. This consensus was noteworthy for fostering a consistent approach to maintaining classroom order and promoting positive student behavior.

These findings had practical implications for school administrators and educators. The high level of disciplinary self-efficacy suggested a strong foundation for effective classroom management and student engagement. However, it was important to continue supporting educators in professional development efforts to enhance their skills and address any specific challenges that may arise. Additionally, leveraging the identified strengths in disciplinary self-efficacy could contribute to creating a positive and conducive learning environment for students.

Overall, these results provided valuable insights into the educators' confidence in their disciplinary abilities, serving as a basis for continued improvement and support within the educational community. The results implied that other factors affected the teaching competencies of the teachers not just limited to the availability of school facilities, instructional materials, and extent of instructional support. According to Jamaluddin and Cadir (2019), due to the insecurities of the teachers they tried to seek more training and preparations to become highly specialized in their teaching efficacy.

Table 9. Respondents' Assessment of their Self-Efficacy in terms of Efficacy to Enlist Parental Support

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. How much can you do to get parents to become involved in school activities?	4.73	0.45	Very High
2. How much can you assist parents in helping their children do well in school?	4.83	0.38	Very High
3. How much can you do to make parents feel comfortable coming to school?	4.75	0.43	Very High
4. How much can you do to get community groups involved in working with the school?	4.73	0.45	Very High
5. How much can you do to get Barangay Officials, and Municipal Officials involved in working with the school?	4.97	0.18	Very High
Total Measure	4.80	0.26	Very High

Note: Scale; Responses; Description; 1.00-1.49; Nothing; Very Low; 1.50-2.49; Very Little; Low; 2.50-3.49; Some Influence; Average; 3.50-4.49; Quite a Bit; High; 4.50-5.00; A Great Deal; Very High

Table 9 displays the respondents' assessment of their self-efficacy in terms of enlisting parental support, with mean and standard deviation (SD) values provided for each indicator. The overall mean score for the efficacy of enlisting parental support was 4.80, and the standard deviation was 0.26, indicating a very high and consistent level of perceived self-efficacy in this domain.

The educators expressed a strong belief in their ability to engage parents and community stakeholders. The highest mean score was associated with the respondents' confidence in involving Barangay Officials and Municipal Officials in working with the school, with a mean score of 4.97. This suggested a high level of confidence in building collaborative relationships with local authorities. Other indicators, such as getting parents involved in school activities ($M=4.73$), assisting parents in supporting their children's education ($M=4.83$), and making parents feel comfortable coming to school ($M=4.75$), also received high mean scores, emphasizing the educators' efficacy in fostering parental involvement.

The low standard deviations across all indicators indicated a high level of agreement among respondents regarding their efficacy in enlisting parental support, suggesting a shared perception of competence in engaging and collaborating with parents and community members.

These results implied that the educators' high level of self-efficacy in enlisting parental support suggested a positive foundation for

building strong partnerships between the school and the community. This may contribute to enhanced student success and overall school effectiveness. These findings also agreed with the recent study by Wairimu et al. (2019). The group of Wairimu generalized that parents' engagement by constant communicating with teachers also decreases chronic absenteeism, or missing more than twenty days of a school year.

On the other hand, Wairimu et al. (2019) reported that when teachers engaged with parents on home visits, for example, student absences dropped by 20%. Even after accounting for the grade level and previous absences, students with communicating parents reported fewer days of school missed overall (Epstein, 2005). Two-way communication between parents and teachers committed students to daily attendance and raised class participation levels was also tackled as reported by Wairimu et al. (2019).

Table 10. Respondents' Assessment of their Self-Efficacy in terms of Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. How much can you do to make the school a safe place?	4.80	0.40	Very High
2. How much can you do to make students enjoy coming to school?	4.83	0.38	Very High
3. How much can you do to get students to trust teachers?	4.75	0.43	Very High
4. How much can you help other teachers with their teaching skills?	4.73	0.45	Very High
5. How much can you do to enhance collaborative between teachers and the administration to make the school run effectively?	4.97	0.18	Very High
6 How much can you do to reduce school absenteeism?	4.80	0.40	Very High
7. How much can you do to reduce school dropout?	4.73	0.45	Very High
8. How much can you do to get students to believe they do well in schoolwork?	4.98	0.16	Very High
9. How much can you do in attempting to teach students who are poorly motivated?	4.93	0.26	Very High
Total Measure	4.83	0.16	Very High

Note: Scale; Responses; Description; 1.00-1.49; Nothing; Very Low; 1.50-2.49; Very Little; Low; 2.50-3.49; Some Influence; Average; 3.50-4.49; Quite a Bit; High; 4.50-5.00; A Great Deal; Very High

Table 10 details the respondents' assessment of their self-efficacy in terms of creating a positive school climate, with mean and standard deviation (SD) values provided for each indicator. The overall mean score for the efficacy of creating a positive school climate was 4.83, and the standard deviation was 0.16, indicating a very high and consistent level of perceived self-efficacy in this crucial aspect of education.

The educators expressed a high level of confidence in their ability to contribute to a positive school environment. Notably, the highest mean score was associated with the respondents' belief in their capacity to enhance collaboration between teachers and administration to make the school run effectively, with a mean score of 4.97. This suggested a strong sense of efficacy in fostering teamwork and communication within the school community. Other indicators, such as making the school a safe place ($M=4.80$), making students enjoy coming to school ($M=4.83$), and helping students believe they do well in schoolwork ($M=4.98$), also received high mean scores, emphasizing the educators' efficacy in creating a safe, engaging, and positive learning environment.

The low standard deviations across all indicators indicated a high level of agreement among respondents regarding their efficacy in creating a positive school climate, reinforcing the overall consistency in their perceptions of competence in this domain. These results provided significant implications that the educators' collective high level of self-efficacy in creating a positive school climate suggests a foundation for a supportive and enriching learning environment. Recognizing and reinforcing the educators' confidence in their ability to shape a positive school climate was essential for sustaining a thriving educational community.

"School climate included major spheres of school life such as safety, relationships, teaching and learning, and the environment as well as larger organizational patterns (e.g. from fragmented to shared; healthy or unhealthy)." These dimensions shaped learning and student development in addition to how students felt about attending school, according to the National School Climate Center (National School Climate Center, 2019).

Table 11. Consolidated Findings of the Respondents' Assessment of their Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Instructional Self-Efficacy	4.83	0.12	Very High
Disciplinary Self-Efficacy	4.83	0.18	Very High
Efficacy to Enlist Parental Support	4.80	0.26	Very High
Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate	4.83	0.16	Very High
Total Measure	4.82	0.16	Very High

Note: Scale; Responses; Description; 1.00-1.49; Nothing; Very Low; 1.50-2.49; Very Little; Low; 2.50-3.49; Some Influence; Average; 3.50-4.49; Quite a Bit; High; 4.50-5.00; A Great Deal; Very High

Table 11 provides a consolidated overview of the respondents' self-efficacy across various domains, presenting mean and standard deviation (SD) values for instructional self-efficacy, disciplinary self-efficacy, efficacy to enlist parental support, efficacy to create a positive school climate, and the overall total measure. The results revealed consistently high levels of perceived self-efficacy across all categories.

For instructional self-efficacy, the mean score was 4.83 with a low SD of 0.12, indicating a very high and homogeneous level of

confidence among the educators in their instructional abilities. Similarly, disciplinary self-efficacy was rated at 4.83 with a slightly higher SD of 0.18, suggesting a slightly greater variability in responses but still reflecting a very high overall level of perceived competence in managing disciplinary aspects.

The respondents demonstrated a high level of efficacy in enlisting parental support, with a mean score of 4.80 and an SD of 0.26, indicating collective confidence in their ability to engage parents and community stakeholders. Furthermore, their efficacy in creating a positive school climate was also rated very high, with a mean score of 4.83 and a low SD of 0.16, suggesting a shared belief in their capacity to contribute to a positive and supportive learning environment.

The overall total measure was 4.82, with a low SD of 0.16, highlighting a consistent and very high level of perceived self-efficacy across all assessed domains. These consolidated findings underscored the educators' confidence in their instructional, disciplinary, parental engagement, and school climate management skills, collectively contributing to a positive and effective educational environment. These results could serve as a foundation for recognizing and capitalizing on the strengths within the educational community, while also identifying potential areas for targeted support and professional development.

A distinction had to be made between teacher self-efficacy and teaching efficacy (Gibson & Dembo, 2019). While teachers' efficacy beliefs, or outcome expectations, referred to teachers' beliefs about the likely consequences of performing specific tasks/behaviors at specific levels of competence, teacher self-efficacy reflected the degree to which teachers evaluated their abilities to bring about positive student change in the face of unforeseen difficulties (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2021). Another central feature of the concept of teacher self-efficacy in Bandura's view was its context specificity. Bandura conceptualized self-efficacy as task-, realm- or domain-specific, meaning that individuals could hold very different levels of self-efficacy beliefs for different behavioral domains (Bandura, 1997), such as classroom management, student engagement, or instructional practices (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2021).

Problem 3: What is the performance of the respondents based on their IPCRF rating?

Table 12. Teaching Performance of the Respondents

<i>Teaching Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Outstanding	8	6.7
Very Satisfactory	112	93.3
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.0
Total	120	100.0

Table 12 provides an overview of the teaching performance of the respondents, categorizing them into different levels of achievement. The majority of respondents, comprising 93.3%, received a rating of "Very Satisfactory," indicating a high level of overall performance in their teaching roles. A smaller proportion, 6.7%, achieved an "Outstanding" rating, signifying an exceptional level of teaching proficiency. Notably, there were no respondents classified under "Fairly Satisfactory," suggesting a lack of individuals falling below a satisfactory level of teaching performance in the sample.

These results painted a positive picture of the overall teaching performance within the surveyed group. The high percentage of "Very Satisfactory" ratings reflected a strong and consistent level of competence and effectiveness among educators. The presence of an "Outstanding" category further highlighted the exceptional contributions of a subset of respondents, showcasing the potential for exemplary teaching practices within the community.

Moreover, teachers were encouraged to do meaningful activities for their professional learning and growth (Junio-Sabio & Manalo, 2020). It could be noted that the teachers were provided with good internal and external forces such as environment, social interaction, and personal motivation that contributed to the quality of teaching performance (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020).

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and self-efficacy?

Table 13 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and various demographic factors. The regression analysis showed that age was not a significant predictor of teachers' self-efficacy, as indicated by the p-values for the age categories (31-45, 46-55, 56-64) being greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. This suggested that the age of the teachers in the study did not have a statistically significant impact on their self-efficacy. Similar to age, gender did not emerge as a significant predictor of teachers' self-efficacy. The p-value for the male gender category was 0.385, exceeding the significance level of 0.05. This implied that, within the context of this study, there was no statistically significant difference in self-efficacy between male and female teachers.

The civil status of teachers, however, showed significant associations with self-efficacy. Specifically, being married or widowed is associated with lower self-efficacy compared to being single. The negative estimates for married and widowed categories indicated a decrease in self-efficacy compared to the reference category (single). This suggested that marital status may influence teachers' self-efficacy perceptions, warranting further exploration into the reasons behind this relationship.

The analysis did not find a significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and their educational attainment (college vs. master's degree). The p-value for the Master's category was 0.302, suggesting that having a Master's degree did not significantly predict higher

or lower self-efficacy in this sample. The number of years in a teaching position also did not emerge as a significant predictor of self-efficacy. The p-values for the categories 11-20 and 21-40 were greater than 0.05, indicating that the duration of teaching experience did not have a statistically significant impact on self-efficacy.

Table 13. *Regression Analysis of Relating Teachers' Self-Efficacy on their Profile*

Profile	Estimate	SE	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age					
Below-30	Ref	--	--	--	--
31-45	.09	.05	1.88	.063	Not significant
46-55	.06	.05	1.15	.254	Not significant
56-64	.04	.05	.85	.398	Not significant
Gender					
Female	Ref	--	--	--	--
Male	.05	.06	.87	.385	Not significant
Civil Status					
Single	Ref	--	--	--	--
Married	-.17	.04	-3.93***	<.001	Significant
Widowed	-.14	.07	-2.10*	.038	Significant
Educational Attainment					
College	Ref	--	--	--	--
Master	-.03	.03	-1.04	.302	Not significant
Years in Teaching Position					
1-10	Ref	--	--	--	--
11-20	-.05	.07	-.65	.518	Not significant
21-40	.04	.07	.57	.572	Not significant

Note: Adjusted $R^2 = .110$ ANOVA for Regression: $F=2.63$, $p=.009$ ***significant at .001 level *significant at .05 level

The findings emphasized that certain demographic factors, such as age and gender, may not be strong predictors of teachers' self-efficacy in this context. These challenges preconceived notions and highlighted the importance of considering individual differences. The significant impact of civil status on self-efficacy suggested that personal factors beyond professional characteristics may play a role in teachers' confidence and perceptions of their abilities. While educational attainment and years in a teaching position did not show significant associations, it was essential to recognize that other factors not included in this analysis may contribute to variations in self-efficacy.

The overall adjusted R^2 value of 0.110 indicated that the model explained a modest proportion of the variance in teachers' self-efficacy, suggesting the presence of additional unexamined factors influencing self-efficacy.

The teaching abilities of teachers and their marital status had a substantial correlation, according to Shah et al. (2018). According to their research, there was a correlation between job discontent and marital dissatisfaction, and this relationship affected how well teachers educate. Because they considered their families, who required their support, married instructors were happier than single teachers.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the self-efficacy of respondents and their IPCRF teaching performance rating?

Table 14. *Regression Analysis of Relating Teachers' Teaching Performance on their Self-Efficacy*

Self-Efficacy	Estimate	SE	Z-value	p-value	Remarks
Instructional Self-Efficacy	-6.72	8.87	-.77	.442	Not significant
Disciplinary Self-Efficacy	-14.12	15.66	-.90	.367	Not significant
Efficacy to Enlist Parental Support	-7.22	6.81	-1.06	.289	Not significant
Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate	38.07	29.45	1.292	.196	Not significant

Note: Based on Binomial Logistic Regression $R^2=.116$

Table 14 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between teachers' teaching performance and their self-efficacy in various domains. The regression analysis indicated that instructional self-efficacy was not a significant predictor of teaching performance. The p-value for instructional self-efficacy was 0.442, exceeding the conventional significance level of 0.05. This suggested that, within the context of this study, there was no statistically significant relationship between teachers' confidence in their instructional abilities and their overall teaching performance. Similarly, disciplinary self-efficacy did not emerge as a significant predictor of teaching performance. The p-value for disciplinary self-efficacy was 0.367, indicating that the perceived ability to manage discipline-related aspects was not significantly associated with overall teaching performance.

The regression analysis suggested that efficacy in enlisting parental support was not a significant predictor of teaching performance. The p-value for this variable was 0.289, indicating that teachers' confidence in engaging parents did not have a statistically significant impact on their overall teaching performance. The efficacy of creating a positive school climate showed no significant association with teaching performance. The p-value for this variable was 0.196, exceeding the conventional significance level. This suggested that

teachers' confidence in fostering a positive school environment was not a statistically significant predictor of their teaching performance.

The lack of significant associations between various domains of self-efficacy and teaching performance in this study challenged the assumption of a direct and linear relationship between these factors. It suggested that teaching performance was likely influenced by a multitude of factors beyond teachers' self-efficacy, and these factors may vary in their impact. The findings underscored the importance of considering a holistic set of factors, including instructional, disciplinary, and interpersonal aspects, when assessing and enhancing teaching performance.

The overall R² value of 0.116 indicated that the model explained a modest proportion of the variance in teaching performance, reinforcing the need for a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of effective teaching.

One of the most crucial factors taken into account when creating the educational system, according to Shah et al. (2020), was the demographics of the teachers. But among the most important components in educational establishments is the performance review. Teachers would be more motivated and do their jobs more effectively if they had such.

Problem 6: Which of the socio-economic profiles and the extent of self-efficacy variables significantly predict the teaching performance of the respondents?

Table 15 presents the results of a regression analysis exploring the relationship between teachers' teaching performance and their self-efficacy, as well as socio-economic profiles. None of the self-efficacy variables showed a significant relationship with teaching performance. The p-values for instructional self-efficacy, disciplinary self-efficacy, efficacy to enlist parental support, and efficacy to create a positive school climate were all above the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that teachers' perceived efficacy in these domains did not significantly predict teaching performance.

The analysis did not find a significant relationship between age and teaching performance. The p-values for the age categories (31-45, 46-55, 56-64) were all greater than 0.05, suggesting that age was not a statistically significant predictor of teaching performance in this study. Similarly, gender did not emerge as a significant predictor of teaching performance. The p-value for the male gender category was 0.999, indicating that, within the context of this study, there was no statistically significant difference in teaching performance between male and female teachers.

Table 15. *Regression Analysis of Relating Teachers' Teaching Performance on their Self-Efficacy and Socio-Economic Profiles*

Predictors	Estimate	Z-value	p-value	Remarks
Instructional Self-Efficacy	246.61	-.002	.998	Not significant
Disciplinary Self-Efficacy	-275.27	-.003	.997	Not significant
Efficacy to Enlist Parental Support	-96.12	-.006	.995	Not significant
Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate	343.91	.006	.995	Not significant
Age				
Below-30	Ref			
31-45	-29.98	-.003	.998	Not significant
46-55	-29.09	-.002	.998	Not significant
56-64	-57.96	-.003	.998	Not significant
Sex				
Female	Ref			
Male	-20.63	-.001	.999	Not significant
Civil Status				
Single	Ref			
Married	27.80	.002	.998	Not significant
Widowed	-2.48	.000	1.000	Not significant
Educational Attainment				
College	Ref			
Master	.79	.604	.546	Not significant
Years in Teaching Position				
1-10	Ref			
11-20	36.90	.002	.999	Not significant
21-40	17.82	.000	.999	Not significant

Note: Based on Binomial Logistic Regression R²=.297

Civil status was also not a significant predictor of teaching performance. The p-values for the married and widowed categories were both above 0.05, suggesting that civil status did not have a statistically significant impact on teaching performance. The analysis did not find a significant relationship between educational attainment and teaching performance. The p-value for the Master's degree category was 0.546, indicating that having a Master's degree was not a statistically significant predictor of teaching performance.

Similarly, the number of years in a teaching position did not emerge as a significant predictor of teaching performance. The p-values

for the 11-20 and 21-40 years categories were both above 0.05, suggesting that the duration of teaching experience did not have a statistically significant impact on teaching performance.

The lack of significant associations between self-efficacy variables and teaching performance underscored the importance of considering various factors that contributed to effective teaching beyond teachers' perceived confidence. The non-significant relationships between socio-economic profiles (age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, years in teaching position) and teaching performance suggested that these demographic factors may not be strong predictors of overall teaching effectiveness within the context of this study.

The overall R² value of 0.297 indicated that the model explained a modest proportion of the variance in teaching performance, highlighting the need for a more comprehensive understanding of the complex factors influencing teachers' effectiveness.

According to Kiamba et al. (2019), teachers' intellectual resources and dispositions largely determined their capacity to engage students' minds and hearts in the learning process. Teachers' subject matter knowledge may be affected by the attitudes and expectations that their students bring to the classroom. Teachers' understanding of the subject matter affected their capacity to simplify content. This helped students to understand. Ademulegun (2019) added that students taught by teachers who were more qualified and experienced in terms of the subject matter performed better than those taught by far less qualified and experienced teachers.

Problem 7: What training program can be designed to increase teachers' efficacy based on the results of the study?

Rationale

The proposed training program is designed to address the nuanced findings of the study, which revealed a lack of significant associations between teachers' self-efficacy, socio-economic profiles, and their teaching performance. Recognizing the multifaceted nature of effective teaching, the program aims to strategically target specific domains identified in the study—instructional methods, classroom discipline, parental engagement, and school climate. By tailoring workshops to these key areas, the training program seeks to empower teachers with practical strategies and skills that extend beyond traditional notions of self-efficacy. Active learning methods, peer collaboration, and ongoing support mechanisms are integrated to ensure the program's effectiveness and relevance.

Additionally, recognizing the role of technology in modern education, the program includes a component focused on enhancing teachers' technological proficiency. This comprehensive approach aims not only to enhance teachers' confidence but also to cultivate a positive and collaborative school culture, fostering continuous professional development. Through these initiatives, the training program intends to create a dynamic and supportive learning environment that aligns with the complex and diverse demands of effective teaching.

<i>Objective</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Timeline</i>	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>Evaluation/Assessment</i>
Increase Instructional Self-Efficacy	Conduct workshops on effective instructional strategies, incorporating peer demonstrations and collaborative planning sessions	4 months	Professional Development Coordinator	Pre and post-training self-assessment surveys; Classroom observations by peers or mentors
Enhance Disciplinary Self-Efficacy	Provide training on positive behavior management strategies, conflict resolution, and classroom discipline techniques	3 months	School Counselor and Disciplinary Committee	Pre and post-training surveys; Behavior incident reports analysis
Strengthen Efficacy to Enlist Parental Support	Offer workshops on building positive parent-teacher relationships, communication strategies, and involving parents in school activities	6 months	Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) and School Administrators	Pre and post-training surveys; Increased parental involvement metrics
Foster Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate	Implement sessions on creating a positive school culture, team-building activities, and collaborative projects among staff	5 months	School Leadership Team	Staff feedback surveys; Observation of staff collaboration and morale
Develop Technological Proficiency	Conduct training sessions on integrating technology into teaching for interactive and engaging lessons	2 months	IT Department and External Facilitators	Pre and post-training technology integration assessments; Classroom observations
Cultivate Continuous Professional Development	Establish a structured mentorship program, encourage participation in conferences, and provide ongoing access to relevant resources	Ongoing	Professional Development Coordinator and Mentors	Regular mentor-mentee evaluations; Participation records in professional development activities

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

This study concluded that educators exhibited consistently high levels of perceived competence across various domains, reflecting robust self-efficacy in instructional, disciplinary, parental engagement, and school climate management skills. The results indicated a commendable standard of teaching performance, with the majority of respondents receiving a "Very Satisfactory" rating and a noteworthy percentage achieving an "Outstanding" rating, highlighting an overall proficiency in their educational roles. The findings collectively underscored a positive foundation for an effective and supportive learning environment.

In exploring the demographic factors influencing teachers' self-efficacy, age and gender did not emerge as significant predictors, suggesting that these variables did not significantly impact educators' confidence levels. However, civil status demonstrated associations with self-efficacy, revealing lower confidence among married or widowed individuals. Notably, educational attainment and the number of years in a teaching position did not show significant relationships with self-efficacy, emphasizing the complexity of factors influencing teachers' perceived competence.

Furthermore, the study found no significant associations between teachers' self-efficacy in various domains and their teaching performance, as well as socio-economic profiles. This suggested that while educators expressed confidence in their instructional, disciplinary, and interpersonal skills, these self-perceptions may not be strong predictors of overall teaching effectiveness. The non-significant relationships indicated that additional factors, beyond self-efficacy and demographic variables, may play pivotal roles in determining teachers' success in the classroom.

Thus, these insights emphasized the nuanced and multifaceted nature of teaching competence, emphasizing the need for a holistic understanding of the factors shaping educators' confidence and performance. The study provided valuable contributions to the field by shedding light on the intricate dynamics influencing teachers' efficacy and performance, ultimately contributing to ongoing efforts to enhance the quality of education in diverse educational settings.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

For school administrators, the findings suggested a need for targeted professional development programs that build on teachers' existing strengths while addressing areas identified as potential challenges. Recognizing the consistently high levels of self-efficacy among educators, administrators can tailor training initiatives to further enhance instructional, disciplinary, and interpersonal skills. Moreover, fostering a positive school climate and encouraging collaborative learning environments can contribute to sustaining teachers' confidence and, consequently, their overall effectiveness. Additionally, administrators should consider incorporating regular feedback mechanisms and support systems to continuously nurture and reinforce teachers' self-efficacy.

Teachers can leverage the study's insights to engage in reflective practices that capitalize on their perceived strengths and address potential areas for growth. Collaborative professional learning communities can provide a platform for educators to share best practices, discuss challenges, and collectively enhance their instructional and interpersonal skills.

Parents play a crucial role in reinforcing educators' efforts by actively participating in school activities and demonstrating a commitment to their children's education. Building partnerships between schools and parents can strengthen the support system for teachers and enhance the overall educational experience. Parents are encouraged to engage in open communication with teachers, attend parent-teacher conferences, and actively participate in school events. Recognizing and appreciating teachers' efforts can contribute to a positive and collaborative school community.

Learners can benefit from the study's insights by actively participating in their educational journey. Engaging in a positive and respectful manner with teachers, being open to different teaching methodologies, and taking initiative in their learning process can contribute to a supportive classroom environment. Additionally, learners should utilize available resources, seek assistance when needed, and actively communicate with teachers to foster a constructive and collaborative learning experience.

For future researchers, this study suggests avenues for further exploration into the dynamics of teachers' self-efficacy and its relationship with various factors. Investigating the impact of specific professional development interventions on teachers' self-efficacy and performance could provide valuable insights. Additionally, exploring the role of school leadership, curriculum design, and classroom dynamics in shaping teachers' perceptions and effectiveness would contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing educational outcomes.

References

- Achurra, C. & Villardon, L. (2019). Teacher self-efficacy and student learning https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269557188_Teacher'_Self-Efficacy_And_Student_Learning.
- Ademulegun, S. R. (2019). A comparative study of weekend developmental curriculum in Davao City, Philippines. *Research Journal*.

- Artino A. R., Jr (2016). Self-efficacy beliefs: From educational theory to instructional practice. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>.
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. <https://link.springer.com>
- Bandura A. (1997). Theory of self-efficacy. https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_1167-1.
- Bates, R. & Clark, B.N. (2018). Self-efficacy beliefs and teacher effectiveness: Implications for professional development. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/pdf>.
- Bauman, W., Marcha, J., Mclain, K. O'connel, M., & Patterson, S. (2018). Teaching the millennial generation in the religious and theological studies classroom. Teaching theology and region chw.org.
- Biyani, A.A., Bagheri H., & Bayani, A. (2019). Influence of gender, age, and years of teaching experience on burnout. *Annals of Biological Research*.
- Bodhe C.D., & Jankar D. S. (2019). Teaching effectiveness: How do students evaluate their teacher? *International J. of Healthcare and Biomedical Research*, Volume 63, Issue: 02, January 2015. Pp. 155-159.
- Chowdhury, M.R. (2019). 4 ways to improve and increase self-efficacy. <https://positivepsychology.com>
- Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Educational research*. 4th Ed. Boston, M.A: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Dalanon, J. & Matsuka, Y. (2017). Filipino teachers' sense of efficacy in inclusion classes. eric.ed.gov.
- Donohoo, J. (2018). Collective teacher efficacy research: Productive patterns of behavior and other positive consequences. <https://link.springer.com>.
- Dukuzumuremyi, S. & Siklander, P. (2018). Interactions between pupils and their teacher in collaborative and technology-enhanced learning settings in the inclusive classroom. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>.
- Ferreira, L. (2018). *Managing change: The measurement of teacher self-efficacy in technology-enhanced student-centered learning environments*. Royal Roads University.
- Gibson, A., & Dembo, L. (2019). Teaching efficacy program national public school holiday. *Research Journal*.
- Lurea, C. (2018). Classroom environment between stimulation and discouragement. teacher's contribution to creating a new socio-affective environment favoring teacher-student communication. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
- Jaminal, B. (2019). The impact of school facilities on the teaching and learning environment. *SMCC Higher Educational Journal*. 12, 42– 54.
- Johnson, L., Becker, S., Cummins, M., Estrada, V., Freeman, A., & Hall, C. (2019). NMC new horizon report: 2016 higher education edition (pp. 1-150). The New Media Consortium.
- Jubran, A. M. (2015). Educational leadership: A new trend that society needs. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>.
- Junio-Sabio, S. & Manalo, J. (2020). Investigating the relationship between teaching pedagogy and academic achievements through geographically weighted regression. *Annals of GIS*, 22(4), 273-285
- Khurshid, R., Qasmi, Z., & As-huraf, Y. (2019). Impact of the implementation of language program in the Philippines. *Educational Research Journal*; Vol. 2 (27-32).
- Kiamba, C., Tores, K., & Roseter, H. (2019). How to sustain students' motivation in a learning environment. Online Submission. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*.
- Köseoğlu, Y. (2015). Self-efficacy and academic achievement – A case study. www.iiste.org
- Leigo, M. A. (2019). Individual performance commitment review form. www.teacherph.com/individual-performance-commitment-review-form-ipcrf/.
- Loveless, B. (2019). Strategies for building a productive and positive learning environment. <https://www.educationcorner.com/building-a-positive-learning-environment.html>.
- Moore, W., & Esselman, M. (2018). Teacher efficacy, empowerment, and a focused instructional climate: Does student achievement benefit? Paper presented at the Annual Conference of the American Educational Research Association, San Francisco. researchgate.net.
- Moran, Hoy, W., & Woolfolk, A. (2019). Teacher efficacy: Capturing an elusive construct. *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Morris, D. (2017). Teaching self-efficacy. <https://oxfordre.com/education/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264093-e-86>.

- Narciso, R. (2017). The education of exceptional children in public elementary schools in Region I. Asia Pacific Institute of Advanced Research.
- Perera, H.N., Calkins, C., & Part, R., (2019). Teacher self-efficacy profiles: Determinants, outcomes, and generalizability across teaching level contemporary educational psychology. *Journals.sagepub.com*.
- Ponders, V.E. (2020). The influence of teachers' biographic attributes and preparation on student achievement in public funds Detroit school Dissertation Abstract International, vol. 84, 62-70.
- Reyes, L. E. (2019). Pedagogy and teaching. *Sage Journals*, 275. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/019263656605031246>.
- Sarabia, K. F., & Colantes, T. (2017). Integrating technology into K-12 teaching and learning: Current knowledge gaps and recommendations for future research. *Education Tech Research Dev*, 2nd, 223–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-006-9022-5>.
- Seralidou, E. & Douligeris, C. (2015). Identification and classification of education collaborative learning environments. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>.
- Sehgal, P. (2015). Teacher effectiveness through self-efficacy, collaboration, and principal leadership. *International Journal of Educational Management*.
- Shah, S., & Udgaonkar, U. (2018). Influence of gender, civil status and age of teachers on teaching: Students' perspective. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*. ISSN: 2319-7706 Volume 7 Number 01 (2018).
- Slade, S. (2017). Learning analytics in higher education: Current innovations, future. *KS.Google.Com*.
- Stanton, T. (2019). The whole school, the whole community, the whole child model: A new approach for improving educational attainment and healthy development for students. *Journal of School Health*, 85 (11), 729-739.
- Tschannen-Moran, K. & Woolfolk, H. (2021). Influence of marital status on teachers' self-efficacy in secondary schools of Kisumu County, Kenya. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*. Imperatives of effective instructional delivery in physical education in secondary schools. *Studies in education*, Vol. 11, 48 – 64.
- Vygotsky, L. (1962). Mind in society: Development of higher psychological processes. <http://www.parentcentredparenting.com/>.
- Wairimu, A. Harad, K. & Benjier, D. (2019). Challenges in the implementation of teaching pedagogy courses program. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, Volume 4, Issue 9, pp. 17-26, 2022.
- Webster's Third New International Dictionary, (1961), Boston, MA: G&C Meriam Company.
- Zhang, X., Meng Y., De Pablos O. P., & Sun, Y. (2017). Learning analytics in collaborative learning supported by Slack: From the perspective of engagement. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Norjehan M. Sangcad

St. Peters' College – Philippines

Dr. Carlito A. Abarquez

St. Peters' College – Philippines